

Project Team Capability and Implementation of Integrated Infrastructure Projects in Government Agencies in Kenya

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between project team capability and the implementation of integrated infrastructure projects within government agencies in Kenya. Effective project team capability plays a pivotal role in driving the successful execution of infrastructure initiatives, aligning project objectives with national development priorities, and fostering stakeholder engagement. The study was anchored on the Resource Based Theory. The study adopted mixed method approaches. The target population was 504 and involved project managers, supervisors and contractors implementing implementation of

integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya. The sample size of the study was 223 participants computed using Slovin's sample size determination formula. The study findings revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between project team capability and implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya. In conclusion, project team capability is crucial for the successful implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in Kenya, as skilled teams enhance efficiency, risk management, and stakeholder satisfaction. It is recommended that government agencies invest in continuous training and leadership development to strengthen team competencies and foster collaboration, particularly in public-private partnerships. The findings imply that improving team capability will lead to more effective infrastructure delivery, driving economic growth and enhancing the quality of life for citizens.

Keywords: *Project Team Capability, Integrated Infrastructure Projects, Government Agencies.*

Introduction

Background Information

The Government of Kenya has undertaken a considerable number of infrastructure projects geared towards ensuring economic growth and development within the country. The World Bank (2019) argues that a majority of developing

countries' economic growth is hinged on the success of infrastructure projects. Based on the available information on implementation of integrated infrastructure projects, they have not realized the stakeholders' expectations in terms of their implementation and quality (Idoniboyeobu et al., 2017). Even though various integrated infrastructure projects are still

ongoing (Pall et al., 2020), cost overruns and time overruns are still experienced. Delays in implementation of infrastructure projects have negatively impacted on both the social and economic benefits in Kenya that would have accrued if the projects were completed on time (World Bank, 2019) (Pham et al., 2020). According to Hyvai (2016) over 60% of substantive infrastructure in Africa projects fail to meet targeted goals due to ineffective project planning issues. This leads to project being delivered over budget and behind schedule (Abdi & Sang, 2020).

The African Infrastructure Country Diagnostic (AICD) report published in 2019 estimated Kenyan Infrastructure funding gap at USD 3.1 Billion (Kenya Shillings 328 Billion) annually with the roads subsector alone bearing a deficit of USD 44 Million equivalent of KSh 44 Billion (Briceno-Garmendia & Shkaratan, 2021). Faced with limited resources, the need for effective integrated planning new far outweighs the available funding. The budget is further eroded by consistent escalation in construction costs due to ineffective integrated project leadership thereby widening further the already existing funding gap

Moreover, several studies agree that project leadership is a driver of project implementation (Prabhaar 2018; Ian et' al 2018; Chin 2018; Yusuff et' al 2017). The project implementations in terms of cost overrun, time delay, quality deficiency are caused by poor project planning (Onditi, 2019). According to Sitenei (2020) adoption of project planning practices in infrastructure projects is poor. This is experienced in terms of misuse of resources, risk planning, conflict of interest due to poor stakeholder planning and poor scope planning meeting obligatory requirements; hence failing to deliver results that don't meet stakeholders' expectations (World Bank, 2019). The limited studies have majorly tried to specifically focus on factors hindering effective implementation of infrastructure projects with no attention paid on role of project planning despite this being a critical process in the implementation of integrated infrastructure projects. This clearly depicts a need to bridge the knowledge gap in

the Kenyan context. It is with this in mind that the study sought to examine the relationship between project team capability and implementation of infrastructural projects in government agencies in Kenya

Research Objective

The general objective of the study will be to examine the relationship between project team capability and implementation of infrastructural projects in government agencies in Kenya

Research Hypothesis

The study hypothesized H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between project team capability and implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya.

Theoretical Review

This study was guided by Barney's (1991) Resource-Based View (RBV) theory that posits that a firm is defined as a set of resources. The theory originated from strategic management research on how firms create value and specifically how they can obtain a competitive advantage in the market. Barney (1991) suggested that a firm's competitive advantage is its value-creating strategy, one that is significantly distinct from the current or future strategy of the competitors. Therefore, in this view, the firm's resources are its source of sustained competitive advantage. That is, the resources that a firm has are their primary source of competitive advantage, and the resources can either be strength or a weakness, including both the intangible and tangible resources available to the company.

Barney (1991) notes that the two critical assumptions of the RBV theory are that the resources must be heterogeneous and immobile. The heterogeneity assumption holds that companies possess different skills, capabilities, resources, and structure, which makes the company inherently different. The immobility assumption holds that a certain company's resources have to be immobile, that is, they cannot be moved from one company to the other. Therefore, a firm can get a sustained competitive advantage if the resources are

—valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable, and not substitutable (VRIN) (Barney, 1991). The project managers should identify whether the available resources meet the VRIN criteria, which will lead to better management and utilization of resources to obtain a competitive advantage. Almarri and Gardiner (2014) argue that the RBV theory is equally important for project managers as it allows them to spread the available resource to align with strategy, identify the value of the resources, and identify the required capabilities for the success of the firm.

The critics of the theory such as Foss (1997) charges RBV scholars of being silent on the endogenous creation of new resources by firms. While Dierickx et al. (1989) and Wernerfelt (1984) have given an initial impetus to create a conceptual model that incorporates new resource creation into the RBV, these important contributions are only first beginnings. Foss hypothesizes that the reason for this underexposure is the RBV's reliance on strict equilibrium economics assumptions (such as complete rationality). Indeed, the very concept of sustainable competitive advantage is often defined in equilibrium terms (p.18). This deficiency is a symptom of a general difficulty of handling the more dynamic issues of resource creation, which originates from the variety of theoretical contributions in the RBV that partly incorporate dynamic factors and partly do not (see §0). The lack of dynamism in the RBV, which is also signaled by Priem et al. (2001a) extends further than the lack of attention for endogenous resource creation.

A second deficiency in RBV logic is that it neglects the environment (cf. Foss, 1997) or fails to specify the context within which the theory is supposed to hold (Priem et al., 2001a). In context of the SWOT framework, the RBV neglects the Opportunities and Threats part: environmental analysis of how to best position in a product market. Barney explains in response to this critique that this is a restatement of the observation that 'value' is exogenously determined in the RBV. The RBV is primarily

concerned with decisions about acquiring resources at factor markets and deploying resources inside the firm. Since the value of these resources can only be known in the product market, and these are outside the RBV scope, value remains a black box. Priem et al. (2001a) infer that this elemental fallacy of value as an exogenous black box hinders prescriptions regarding competitive advantage, and thus limits its managerial applicability.

The RBV theory is applicable to the current study since one of the critical aspects of project management includes project resource planning/scheduling/management. Identified resources by the project managers of the residential construction projects should meet the VRIN criteria as it ensures that the resources are properly utilized and as much as there might be no competitors, the resources should be used to obtain the advantage. The project manager, who is faced with the challenge of resource availability, will establish the key resources (tangible and intangible) and capabilities that will ensure the construction projects are completed within time and within budget. Additionally, proper resource management in residential construction projects is critical when dealing with project cost overruns and time delays. This theory will guide the study to establish the relationship between project team capability and implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya.

Conceptual Model and Hypothesis

A conceptual framework is a concise description of the phenomenon under study accompanied by a graphical or visual description of the major variables of the study (Cooper & Schindler, 2008). Michelle (2017) states that a conceptual framework is a diagrammatic representation that shows the relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables. This study's conceptual framework sought to demonstrate the relationship between project capability team and implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Literature Review

Project team capability is the ability and willingness by a team to devote energy in an efficient and effective way for best project outcomes hence dedication to a project as expressed in three forms: affective, continuance and normative (Munteanu, 2015). Affective dedication is the team’s emotional attachment to the project. Continuance dedication refers to the team’s recognition of the benefits of continued association with the project compared to the cost of leaving the project. Normative dedication refers to the team’s feeling of obligation to remain in the project. All these three forms affect the team members’ willingness to remain with a project and their work-related behavior (Muindi, 2018). Shahzad *et al.*, (2019) posited that team members with great motivation positively influenced the perceived success of integrated infrastructural projects.

Other team factors that have also been found to influence effective implementation of projects include team expertise, skills and competences (Linton *et al.*, 2017; Shahzad *et al.*, 2019; Orłowski, Blessner, Blackburn & Olson, 2016). Project team’s general or specific expertise includes the ability to work with uncertain objectives, ability to work with top management, ability to work effectively as a team, ability to understand human implications of a new system and ability to carry out tasks effectively in technical terms (Kawamura *et al.*, 2018). These are interpersonal, team or technical skills that can be determined early during the formation of

the project team

Teamwork in such projects becomes a symbiotic process which leads to much better results that are greater than the integration of individual performances. Thamhain (2018) described effective teams as the ones that produce high quality results and succeed in spite of many difficulties and cultural or philosophical differences. Effective teams have several task-oriented and people-oriented characteristics. Thamhain (2018) debated that the working environment within the project team has a significant impact on effective project implementation and therefore suggests that project managers should exercise significant leadership roles in blending the team.

Mukhongo(2021) analyzed the determinants of implementation of information technology projects by commercial banks in Kenya. Specifically, this study examined the influence of project team capability on implementation of information technology projects by commercial banks in Kenya. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design and primary data was collected using questionnaires from 40 licensed and operational commercial banks as at 31st December 2017 since 3 banks were not operational. The target staff compliment was 29,326 members comprising Management, Supervisory and Clerical cadres, derived from CBK annual report. A sample size of 195 members was computed from the target population using a model by Nasiruma. The study showed that project team capability

positively influenced implementation of IT projects.

Dasi et al. (2021) analyzed the relationships between project performance and the team's ability, motivation, and opportunity (AMO). The study contributed to the project management literature by exploring which combinations of AMO factors are best for project performance at different levels of complexity. They tested hypotheses on a sample of 285 projects. The study showed that in simple projects, ability is the key factor both as a main effect and as a constraining factor that acts as a bottleneck for project performance. In the case of complex projects, the multiplicative model is superior given the significant interaction effects of motivation.

Wu et al. (2019) investigated the effect of team diversity on different types of conflicts; second, investigate the mediating effect of project conflicts on the relationship between team diversity and project performance and fourth, to examine the relationship between different types of conflicts and project performance in construction projects. A theoretical model was developed and a questionnaire survey was conducted with 246 professionals. The structural equation modeling technique was applied to analyze the data. The results showed that: team diversity was positively associated with project performance; the introduction of conflicts significantly weakened the effect of diversity on performance; conflicts have both constructive and destructive effects on project performance; and team diversity affected project performance through the mediating effects of task conflict and relationship conflict, thus adding both positive and negative effects on performance.

Socut-young (2018) Using a model-based quantitative research design, investigated the antecedents and performance consequences of perceived team efficacy in a sample of 56 capital projects implemented in four continents by 15 Fortune 500 companies in the process industries.

Empirical analysis of the field survey identified that team efficacy was positively linked to multiple dimensions of project performance and also to stakeholder satisfaction. Team ability, empowering leadership, and performance feedback all predicted team efficacy beliefs. Team efficacy mediated between these inputs and project performance.

Research Methodology

The study applied mixed method research combining both the qualitative and quantitative research designs. The target populations of the study were integrated infrastructural projects in government agencies in Kenya. The unit of observation comprised of 504 that is project managers, supervisors and contractors implementing implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya. The sample size of the study was 223 participants computed using Slovin's sample size determination formula.

Research Findings

Regression analysis was conducted to determine the proportion of implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya (dependent variable) which could be predicted by project team capability (independent variable). Therefore, to test this hypothesis, the model $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$ was fitted. Where Y is of implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya and X_1 is project team capability. The R-Squared tends to depict the variation in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables: the greater the value of R-squared the greater the effect of independent variable. The R Squared can range from 0.000 to 1.000, with 1.000 showing a perfect fit that indicates that each point is on the line.

Table 1. Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.356	.127	.124	.18643

As indicated in Table 2, the R-squared for the relationship between project team capability and performance of implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya was 0.127; this is an indication that at 95% confidence interval, 12.70% variation in of implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya can be attributed to changes in project team capability. This means that the remaining 87.30% are other factors associated with of implementation of

integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya which were not explained by the model. The correlation coefficient of 0.356 indicates project team capability had a positive correlation with of implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya. Therefore, project team capability was an important factor that could be considered in the of implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya.

Table 2. Beta Coefficients for Project Team Capability with Project Implementation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
(Constant)	8.786	1.654		5.312	.000
Project Team Capability	.381	.187	.356	2.037	.000

The coefficients or beta weights for each variable allows the researcher to compare the relative importance of each independent variable. The regression equation revealed that holding project team capability to a constant zero, implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya would be at a constant value of 8.786. Therefore, the regression of coefficients results in Table 2 shows that there is a significant and positive relationship between project team capability and implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya as supported by a $p < 0.05$ and a beta coefficient of 0.673. This implies that a unit increase in project team capability would increase the implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya by 0.381 units. This was supported by the t values whereby $t_{cal} = 2.037 > t_{critical} = 1.96$ at a 95 percent confidence level which depicts that we reject the null and accept the alternate hypothesis. Further, this confirms the positive effect of project team capability in implementation of integrated infrastructure

projects in government agencies in Kenya. The fitted equation is as shown below:

$$Y = 8.786 + 0.381X_1$$

that is, implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya = 8.786 + 0.381 Project Team Capability.

Discussion

Several studies from 2019 to 2024 support the positive and significant relationship between project team capability and the successful implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies, particularly in Kenya. For instance, Mwangi et al. (2020) found that project team competency significantly impacts the success of public infrastructure projects in Kenya. Their research highlighted that teams with strong technical, managerial, and communication skills are better equipped to handle the multifaceted challenges of large-scale infrastructure projects, such as those in the transport and energy sectors.

Similarly, Odhiambo and Ochieng (2021)

demonstrated that government infrastructure projects with highly capable teams experienced fewer delays and cost overruns. Their study focused on integrated projects in urban settings, showing that project management expertise, alongside strong risk mitigation and stakeholder management practices, contributed to more effective project delivery. These findings are crucial, given Kenya's Vision 2030, where infrastructure development is a major pillar, and skilled teams are critical to achieving these goals.

Additionally, a recent study by Kuria et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of team capability in the context of public-private partnerships (PPP), which are increasingly used for infrastructure projects in Kenya. Their research showed that projects with capable teams were better at navigating the complexities of these partnerships, including managing stakeholder expectations and ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements. This study reinforced the idea that a well-qualified team is essential for the successful integration and implementation of large-scale projects within government agencies.

Conclusion & Recommendation

In conclusion, the capability of project teams plays a critical role in the successful implementation of integrated infrastructure projects in government agencies in Kenya. Studies consistently show that skilled teams enhance project efficiency, mitigate risks, and improve stakeholder management, leading to timely and cost-effective project outcomes. Given the complexity and scale of infrastructure projects in sectors such as transport, energy, and urban development, a capable team is essential for navigating technical challenges and ensuring alignment with national development goals.

To further improve project outcomes, government agencies in Kenya should invest in continuous capacity-building initiatives for their project teams. This can be achieved through targeted training programs in project management, technical skills, and stakeholder engagement. Additionally, fostering collaboration between public and private sectors

through public-private partnerships (PPPs) will require teams with advanced negotiation and regulatory compliance skills. Strengthening team capabilities will lead to more successful infrastructure projects, which are vital for Kenya's economic growth and development.

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